

Stress redistribution capacity of textile-reinforced concrete shells folded utilizing parameterized waterbomb patterns

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Abstract

The development of lightweight, high-performance cementitious composite materials such as carbon concrete has triggered the need for innovative design and construction methods for thin-walled structural elements with an optimal material utilization. Combining the material efficiency of carbon concrete with the form flexibility provided by parameterized origami patterns, such as a waterbomb tessellation, opens up new options for innovative design of high-performance light-weight shell structures. Indeed, the possibility to fold concrete shells in a fresh state of concrete matrix from a planar configuration to a spatial form can be exploited to develop an efficient and customizable construction method that eliminates an expensive, single-use spatial formwork. A crucial question posed in this context is, how to achieve ductile structural behavior with a composite material consisting solely of brittle and quasi-brittle components, i.e. carbon, glass, basalt reinforcement and concrete matrix. Since these materials do not provide any source of ductility on their own, substantially different design approaches compared to traditional steel-reinforced concrete are required, that exploit the stress redistribution effects at the structural level due to debonding and multiple cracking of the composite. To contribute to the understanding of these stress redistribution effects in the context of folded thin-walled spatial shell structures, this paper presents preliminary numerical and experimental studies investigating the structural behavior of shells folded using waterbomb tessellations with varied geometrical parameters. The conducted experiments on folded waterbomb shells made of carbon concrete and produced using the *fold-in-fresh* method [12] are presented showing the potential of this structural concept with a maximum ultimate load 45 times larger than the self weight of the shell. This development serves the aim to optimize thin-walled geometrical forms to reach a high-performance carbon concrete elements with high material utilization in service state, high ductility before failure and high load-to-weight ratio.

Keywords: Waterbomb pattern, folding kinematics, folded shell, TRC, reinforced concrete shell, carbon concrete

1 Introduction

The Japanese paper-folding art of origami has been inspiring engineers and scientists throughout the past decades, and it was found to have useful applications in many fields such as architecture, mechanical engineering, medicine and aerospace. Waterbomb is an origami pattern with six facets meeting at one vertex point in the center, which offers significant form flexibility and structural properties when tessellated and folded [5, 13, 9, 8]. This provides an attractive design space for textile-reinforced concrete (TRC) shells, which were found to be a thin, durable and high performance alternative to the conventional steel-reinforced shells [11, 7, 3, 10]. In addition, efficient shell manufacturing approaches can be developed utilizing the flat-foldability of the waterbomb tessellations. This allows folding the spatial geometry from a plane state using a foldable formwork which exploits the kinematics of an origami tessellation. In this way, a reusable, customizable production process becomes possible, eliminating the need for single-use three-dimensional formworks.

In this paper, a preliminary experimental and numerical investigation of the structural behaviour of waterbomb shells is introduced. In contrast to the numerical form-finding approaches [13, 14], in this work, we generate the target shell geometries using a novel method utilizing an analytical mathematical description for symmetrically folded waterbomb tessellations presented recently in [5]. It will be demonstrated that many solutions, i.e., many waterbomb tessellations, are obtainable for the same target global cylinder geometry. This provides a great advantage from a structural point of view, as different structural properties are obtainable from the various solutions, meaning a richer space to investigate seeking the folded variant with the best structural behaviour.

In the following, we first introduce our approach to generate the different waterbomb shell geometries. Then, the experimental investigation is presented and discussed, followed by the numerical studies on the structural behaviour.

2 Parameterized waterbomb shell geometries

2.1 Kinematics of waterbomb patterns

In a previous work [5], we introduced an analytical description of the folding kinematics of a symmetrically folded waterbomb cell. In addition, a closed form solution for the kinematics of a flat-foldable, arbitrarily large tessellation consisting of waterbomb cells was introduced, from which a wide range of single-curved shells is obtainable by altering the design parameters of the tessellated cells. The geometry of the waterbomb cell is defined by the lengths a , b and c and the folding state is controlled by the angle γ . These four parameters are sufficient to describe the kinematics of the symmetrically folded waterbomb cell at any folding state. In Fig. 1, a waterbomb shell created by tessellating identical waterbomb cells is illustrated. The corresponding cell is also provided in the same figure demonstrating the parameters a , b , c and γ .

2.2 Geometry of the tested shell prototypes

The algebraic solutions of the waterbomb kinematics are used to derive the geometry of the tested TRC waterbomb shell prototypes. The shells consist of 2×2 waterbomb cells with the following parameters ($a = 125$ mm, $b = 550$ mm, $c = 175$ mm, $\gamma = 46^\circ$), see Fig. 2. Because the cells are assembled in an alternating manner, the 2×2 tessellation was obtained by clipping the middle 2×2 cells from 3×3 tessellation to obtain a symmetric pattern as shown in Fig. 2. Then, extension stripes of 5 cm was added along the sides of the pattern to add more material in tensile zones and to facilitate the application of the LVDTs (Linear variable differential transformers) for measuring the deflections at the lowest points at the midspan of the shell. Eventually, by folding the obtained pattern with a folding angle $\gamma = 46^\circ$, the final spatial form of the shell is obtained yielding a span $s = 2120$ mm, a width $w = 500$ mm and a height $h = 280$ mm, see Fig. 2. Additional stiffening elements were also added afterwards, which will be elaborated in a later section.

Figure 1: Folded waterbomb shell with the corresponding base cell, illustrated with the folding parameters a, b, c and γ

Figure 2: Deriving the geometry of the tested waterbomb shells

2.3 Shell form-finding for the numerical studies

Using the analytical description of the waterbomb shell, the coordinates of all shell points can be calculated in each folding state (at each γ value). By setting target geometrical properties such as shell width w , height h and span s in analogy to the shell in Fig. 2, the goal is to obtain the set of folding parameters (a, b, c, γ) that renders the target geometry. Interestingly, the waterbomb kinematics provides the flexibility to achieve the desired global curvature with different densities of the waterbomb cells along x and y directions (n_x, n_y) . In the present study, we set the following target geometrical properties $(s = 2000 \text{ mm}, h = 300 \text{ mm}, w = 500 \text{ mm})$ and we seek the valid folding parameters (b, c, γ) for the design variants with the fixed parameters $(a = 100 \text{ mm}, n_x = 2, n_y = 2)$, $(a = 100 \text{ mm}, n_x = 2, n_y = 2)$, $(a = 150 \text{ mm}, n_x = 2, n_y = 4)$, $(a = 150 \text{ mm}, n_x = 2, n_y = 4)$ following the steps:

1. The quantities $\eta = b/a$ and $\zeta = c/a$ are introduced as dimensionless variants of the lengths b and c .
2. The parameter a and the number of cells n_x, n_y are chosen.
3. For each $\gamma \in [10^\circ, 85^\circ]$ we do the following:

- (a) Calculate the shell span s for shells with fixed a and γ values using different combinations of $\eta \in [0, 10]$ and $\zeta \in [0, 10]$, see Fig. 3 (a) bottom diagram.
 - (b) Extract the longest contour line that corresponds to the target span $s = 2000$ mm using a bilinear interpolation (red curve in Fig. 3 (a) bottom diagram). The extracted contour lines for all $\gamma \in [10^\circ, 85^\circ]$ values are illustrated in Fig. 3(a). The parameter combinations given by each point on these curves produce a waterbomb shell with span $s = 2000$ mm.
 - (c) Calculate the shell height h for all the shells given by the parameters combinations in Fig. 3(a) and interpolate η and ζ values targeting the height $h = 300$ mm. In Fig. 3(b), the interpolated (η, ζ, γ) combinations for the height $h = 300$ mm are illustrated. Also, representative values of η and ζ with $\gamma = 10^\circ$ as one valid parameters combination that yields a span $s = 2000$ mm and a height $h = 300$ mm is demonstrated.
4. Interpolate each parameter from each valid parameters combination $\{(\eta, \zeta, \gamma)_1, \dots, (\eta, \zeta, \gamma)_n\}$ with the corresponding shell width $\{w_1, \dots, w_n\}$ to get the $(\eta, \zeta, \gamma)_{\text{final}}$ satisfying the target width $w = 500$ mm too.

Figure 3: Deriving the shell geometries for the numerical studies, exemplified using diagrams of the shell WBS 3 with $a = 100$ mm and $n_y = 4$

Finally, the folding parameters (a, b, c, γ) for the four target geometries are obtained. By tessellating and folding the waterbomb cells using the corresponding γ angle, the targeted shell forms are obtained as illustrated in Fig. 4. The figure shows also a curved shell with the same geometrical properties, that is provided as a reference for the coming numerical study.

Figure 4: The geometries and the waterbomb folding parameters for the five shells studied numerically

The analytical description of the waterbomb kinematics proposed in [5] provides a direct mapping between the origami tessellation design parameters and the tessellated cylinder geometries. For a given shell curvature a multitude of possible design parameters with different fineness of the tessellation can be identified without the need for iterative numerical shape fitting. This mapping provides the basis for an identification of folded geometries that deliver the best structural behaviour in terms of the load capacity and deformation capacity for a prescribed shape and boundary conditions.

3 Experimental studies

To understand the structural behaviour of waterbomb textile-reinforced concrete shells, a preliminary investigation using a series of four specimens with the geometry presented in Sec. 2.2 was manufactured and tested. To improve the stiffness of the folded shells, they were stiffened by adding two concrete plates with 4 cm thickness into the valley folds (see Fig. 2). Moreover, two variants were used to stiffen the section in midspan, i.e., a wooden plate with thickness 2.1 cm filling the section was used for two shells and a steel rod connecting the lower two points on the sides of the midspan was used for the other two shells.

3.1 Manufacturing of the specimens

The specimens were produced using the fold-in-fresh method, originally introduced in [12], employing a foldable formwork (foldwork), see Fig. 5. The crease pattern with the dimensions 2.2 m × 0.7 m was made up of individual facets of wood, which were connected by hinged bands and mounted in a wooden box on vertical supports at pre-defined positions. These positions were chosen such that the weight between the supports was slightly larger compared to the outside the supports. In this way, the folding

process could be controlled at a low force. The 1 cm thick shells were produced using a fine-grained concrete with compressive strength ranging from $f_{cm} = 72.1$ MPa to $f_{cm} = 93.2$ MPa (see Table. 1) and one unimpregnated carbon textile grid placed in the middle of the shell section, which has a tensile strength $f_t = 1483$ MPa and elasticity modulus $E_f = 180.9$ GPa for the roving. The concrete shell was cast in a flat (unfolded) state using a lamination process. Afterwards, the desired target shape was reached by lifting the formwork vertically using a hand pallet truck situated in the middle with lowering the sides utilizing wires in a controlled manner. Different types of foils were used to prevent concrete from penetrating the hinges. Best results could be achieved with a wide latex film.

Figure 5: Steps for manufacturing of the folded shells: a) foldable formwork; b) laminated fresh concrete; c) folded shell in fresh concrete state; d) after concrete hardening

3.2 Experimental setup

All four shells were tested using a configuration similar to the three point bending test used for the characterization of beam behavior. The displacement controlled load was applied at the middle of the shell after casting a circular area with a layer of concrete to improve the load transfer. Two types of supports were used at the ends of the shell: (1) an inclined steel support without vertical clamping, i.e., the shell sides can slide along the inclined steel support, and (2) a vertical clamping of the boundary sections that mitigated the shell rotation at the boundary and the horizontal sliding. Fig. 6(a) shows the test setup for the shell 1 with the LVDTs utilized to measure shell deflections in different points. A summary of the test setup and results with production details for each specimen is provided in Table 1.

3.3 Test results

The load-deflection curves obtained from the four conducted experiments are illustrated in Fig. 6(b). The differences in the measured curves are due to the iterative improvements of the test setup as indicated by the types of support and stiffening in Table 1. The best performance was obtained for the shell 4 with the maximum ultimate load of 13 kN, a value which is 45 times larger than the self weight (0.3 kN). The qualitative shape of the load-deflection curves was highly non-linear, demonstrating the possibility to introduce a quasi-ductile behavior at the structural level. The non-linear response is owing to the development of transverse tensile cracks as illustrated in Fig. 7. Later, macroscopic cracks developed along the fold lines.

Table 1: Summary of the tests data and results for the four tested waterbomb shells

Shell number		1	2	3	4
Concrete	Age [days]	136	50	126	98
	Compressive strength f_{cm} [MPa]	-	72.1	-	93.2
	Flexural tensile strength $f_{ctm, fl}$ [MPa]	-	11.5	-	12.0
Carbon grid	E-modulus E_f [GPa]	180.9			
	Tensile strength f_t [MPa]	1483			
	Cross-section area [mm ² /m]	53.9			
Test setup	Supports	jointed steel rod	jointed steel rod	jointed wooden plate	partially fixed wooden plate
	Center stiffening				
Results	Maximum load [kN]	7.8	8.5	8.0	13.6
	Corresponding deflection [mm]	8.2	15.3	5.9	15.6

Figure 6: Test setup and load deflection curves of the four tested shells

Figure 7: A bottom view showing crack patterns of the four tested shells

4 Numerical studies

A non-linear finite element analysis was conducted to investigate the structural behaviour of four waterbomb shells with identical curvature and different fineness of the tessellation (WBS 1 to WBS 4) and a

smooth curved shell, which have the same span, height and width. The geometries and the waterbomb folding parameters are illustrated in Fig. 4. To cover the limit cases of the possible boundary conditions, two types of boundary conditions were tested for the five mentioned shells, either fully fixed supports on both sides or with one side left free on y -direction. In both cases, the sides were fixed in x -direction. In addition to the five shells, a stiffened variant of the shell WBS 1 was calculated using fixed supports, see Fig. 8.

a) Boundary conditions

Figure 8: (a) The variants of the boundary conditions used for the FE shell analysis; (b) the geometry of the stiffened WBS 1 shell with the stiffening elements illustrated in red

4.1 Non-linear finite element model

The non-linear FE analysis was performed using the commercial software ATENA [4] utilizing quadratic triangular layered shell elements with five degrees of freedom at each node, i.e., three displacements and two rotations.

A combined fracture–plastic constitutive model, available in ATENA, was used for concrete after adjusting the tensile behaviour to consider the contribution of the textile reinforcement in a smeared manner. Therefore, the stress-strain relation on tension was adapted to represent the response of a TRC plate with the same cross-section and material properties as shell 4 presented in the last section, i.e. 1 cm thick plate with one carbon grid in the middle using concrete compressive strength $f_{cm} = 93.2$ MPa. The composite tensile response was calculated based on the ACK model [1, 2]. The material parameters of the strain-hardening fracture-plastic model have been identified based on the tensile test results in analogy to the approach described in [6].

4.2 Results of the parametric study

The load-deflection curves obtained from the finite element analysis for a displacement-controlled loading at the upper middle edge of the shells are plotted in Fig. 9 for the eleven calculated shells. The deflection is measured in all cases at the lowest point in the shell midspan. The calculation was terminated in each case when the curve starts to descend after passing the peak.

First, we notice a significant influence of the boundary conditions on the load-deflection response indicated by a much higher stiffness and load capacity for variants with fixed supports (continuous curves) in comparison to variants with one roller support (dashed curves). The shells with a roller support demonstrated higher ductility and larger deflections due to the possible horizontal sliding. Also, a major difference is noticeable between the different waterbomb tessellations showing a much higher load for the shells with two cells (WBS 1, WBS 2) in comparison to the shells with four cells (WBS 3, WBS 4).

The smaller effective cross-section height and the smoother surface of the four-cells shells could explain this difference. However, this conclusion cannot be generalized as a better performance is obtained for the fixed WBS 1 shell in comparison to the fixed WBS 2 shell in spite of having a smaller cross-section height.

Figure 9: Load-deflection curves obtained from the FEM analysis of the eleven carbon concrete shells (nine folded waterbomb shells and two curved shells variants)

The fixed variant with stiffening interlock plates put across the origami valleys into the waterbomb shell WBS 1 has shown the best performance yielding 30% higher load capacity in comparison to the WBS 1 variant without interlock plates. As expected, the smooth curved shell showed the lowest load capacity, which demonstrate the significant advantage of the folded geometries. Therefore, even by utilizing a pattern with slightly folded facets, and consequently, a comparable cross-section height to the curved shell case, such as the shell WBS 3, almost eight times higher load capacity is reachable. This might be explained by the better strain and stress distribution in the case of the folded shells in comparison to the smooth variant, as Fig. 10 illustrates.

5 Conclusions

The design and manufacturing method for folded textile-reinforced concrete shells, previously introduced with the name *Oricrete*, was expanded by presenting flexible single-curved shell geometries based on parameterized waterbomb patterns to produce high-performance and highly customizable TRC shell structures.

The numerical study using a non-linear finite element model showed that the varied folding parameters activate different stress redistribution mechanisms and, thus, lead to different load-deflection responses. Consequently, it was demonstrated, that much higher stiffness and load capacity is obtainable using folded geometries in comparison to a curved smooth shell variant. The aim of the current numerical study was to provide a qualitative evaluation of the load-deflection response for waterbomb

Figure 10: Comparison of the distribution of the maximum principal strains of the curved shell and WBS 3 with fixed supports

shells with identical TRC material behaviour and curvature as a preliminary step for the following more comprehensive investigation, for which an improved and validated material model will be developed. The ultimate goal is to find geometric and material configurations producing a structural behaviour with high stiffness and load capacity, efficient material use and ductile failure.

The synergy of the structural shape and the dissipative mechanisms activated at the high level of loading can be exploited to introduce an innovative design concept for light-weight composite shells consisting of purely brittle materials.

Acknowledgement

This work was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – SFB/TRR280, Project-ID 417002380 (C04). The authors acknowledge this support gratefully.

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